

EPOS
ERIC

GENDER
EQUALITY
PLAN

EP**S**
EUROPEAN PLATE OBSERVING SYSTEM

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V1.0 / 13 December 2022	Original Version
V1.1 / 9 October 2023	Assessment of the status of the implementation of the measures; better definition of timeline for Goal 3 and Goal 4; defining and adding "means of verifications"; Goal 2 main objective extended to the executive boards. Addition of Annex 2 - checklist of GEP requirements (ref. Measure 3.1.1)
V1.2 / 3 November 2023	Goal 1 main objective: "Inclusion" added 1.1: better distinction between quantitative and qualitative indicators 1.1.2: training included in the measure and indicator 2.2.2: new measure created (Training the existing bodies about GEP and DEI aspects) Goal 3 main objective targets equality in general, not only focusing on gender equality (e.g., 3.3) 3.1 - 3.2: inclusion of DEI dimension to "b. objective" 3.1.1 and 3.1.2: DEI requirements included in "e. indicators" Goal 4: "diversity and inclusion" added to the main objective (e.g., 4.2) 4.2.1 and 4.2.2: new measures created 5.1 discrimination and have been included Section 3: an introduction to the paragraph has been included
V1.3 / 27 November 2023	3.3.1 Provide equal salary condition: quantitative means of verification added; acknowledged by the General Assembly on 16 December 2023
V1.3.1 / 13 December 2024	Internal monitoring: the state of implementation of each measure (status) has been updated; deadlines have been updated accordingly

Place, date

Signature

EPOS ERIC

GENDER EQUALITY PLAN

Version: 1.3

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Introduction

EPOS, European Plate Observing System (www.epos-eu.org) is a distributed research infrastructure committed to enabling excellent science through the integration, accessibility, use and re-use of solid Earth science data, research products and services, as well as by promoting physical access to research facilities. EPOS brings together solid Earth scientists, national research infrastructures, ICT experts and decision makers to establish and underpin sustainable and long-term access to solid Earth science data and services, integrating diverse European Research Infrastructures under a common federated framework. EPOS relies on Open Science innovation with the goal of developing new concepts and tools to provide accurate, durable, and sustainable answers to societal questions concerning geo-hazards and those geodynamic phenomena (including geo-resources) relevant to the environment and human welfare.

The EPOS vision is to ensure sustainable and universal use and reuse of multidisciplinary solid Earth science data and products fostering state-of-the-art research and innovation.

The EPOS mission is to establish and underpin sustainable and long-term access to solid Earth science data and services integrating diverse European Research Infrastructures under a common federated framework.

On October 30th, 2018, the European Commission granted EPOS the legal status of the European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). The ERIC legal framework provides EPOS with legal status recognised in all EU Member States and with the flexibility to adapt to the specific requirements of each infrastructure. Under this European framework, the EPOS ERIC Gender Equality Plan (GEP) commits to the European Strategy for Gender Equality 2020-2025 and the introduction of the GEP eligibility criterion for Horizon Europe participating organisations and considers goals, actions and resources dedicated to improving gender equality within the organisation and to promote gender equality within the whole EPOS Community.

The EPOS ERIC GEP has been tailored having regard to the EPOS mission and vision, history, and wider context, taking into consideration the results of an internal survey aimed at measuring experiences and perceptions of gender equality in EPOS ERIC (Annex 1). The EPOS ERIC GEP is seen to be a dynamic document that will be monitored and updated if needed, on an annual basis.

The EPOS ERIC GEP complies with the requirements set by the European Commission since it:

- 1) is a public document signed-off by the top management;
- 2) foresees dedicated resources for its monitoring and implementation;
- 3) includes data collection and monitoring processes;
- 4) involves training.

Action Plan

Overview of the goals and action plan

The EPOS ERIC GEP relies on the following goals as recommended in the [Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans](#):

- Goal 1: Work-life balance and organisational culture.
- Goal 2: Gender balance in leadership, decision-making and executive bodies.
- Goal 3: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.
- Goal 4: Integrating the gender dimension into research content.
- Goal 5: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

For each goal, a dedicated table outlines the following aspects:

- a. Number corresponding to the objective (No).
- b. Objectives per each main goal, describing what needs to be achieved (Objective).
- c. Actions to attain the objective (Measure).
- d. Individuals or groups for whom these actions are intended (Target).
- e. Criteria and metrics employed to assess progress and verify the status of each measure (Indicator).
- f. External factors may influence the desired outcomes which do not directly depend on EPOS ERIC (Dependencies).
- g. EPOS ERIC Unit or individuals responsible for the execution of the measure (Responsibility).
- h. The start and end dates for the implementation of each measure (Timeline).
- i. The current state of each measure, evaluated by the end of the year. It includes details on the level of completion (Status).

Human resources from the Executive Coordination Office (ECO) are assigned annually for the data collection, monitoring, and implementation of the EPOS ERIC Gender Equality Plan.

Goal 1. Work-life balance and organisational culture at EPOS ERIC

Main objective: Develop specific measures for work-life balance and promote an organisational culture based on gender equality, diversity and inclusion.

OBJECTIVE 1.1 INCLUSIVE WORK-LIFE BALANCE POLICIES AND PRACTICES					
Measure 1.1.1 Maintain existing measures for the work-life balance including remote working agreements and flexible working time arrangements (e.g., measures like an "hours bank")					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS ERIC Employees	Number of employees benefiting from work-life balance Internal measures Means of verification: quantitative: n° of staff with flexible working time and remote working agreements; qualitative: Results of interviews/surveys	N/A	Administration Unit	2023-2024	The Administration Unit is monitoring the evolution of the working legislation and best practices
Measure 1.1.2 Explore additional measures to facilitate the integration of staff after a break (e.g., parental leave, sick leave, sabbatical leave, etc.)					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS ERIC Employees	Policy supporting the integration of staff after a break. Means of verification: policy in place	N/A	Administration Unit	2023-2024	Ongoing activity. The Administration Unit is working on drafting the policy
OBJECTIVE 1.2 PROMOTE AN ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE BASED ON GENDER EQUALITY					
Measure 1.2.1 Inform the EPOS stakeholders that the EPOS ERIC GEP is in place. Produce and disseminate a public statement supporting gender equality					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS Stakeholders	Dissemination of Public statement supporting gender equality Means of verification: communication distributed to stakeholders	N/A	Communication Unit	2023-2024	The original version of the GEP is available on the EPOS ERIC website. A communication is planned for the release of the updated GEP (Dec23/Jan24)
Measure 1.2.2 Produce and internally disseminate guidelines for equality-oriented language and communication and offer training concerning GEP and other diversity aspects					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023

EPOS Stakeholders	Guidelines and training for equality-oriented language and communication (also referring to available EU material) Means of verification: i) guidelines available and disseminated through the Intranet; ii) training delivered	N/A	Communication Unit	2024	Planned for 2024
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Goal 2. Gender balance in leadership, decision-making and executive bodies (Committees, Boards, Working Groups)

Main objective: Promote and maintain gender balance in EPOS ERIC committees, boards and working groups (e.g., Executive Committee; Service Coordination Committee; Ethics Board; Scientific Board, IT Board, Policies Working Group, GEP Working Group). EPOS ERIC is committed to the provisions of the GEP (see Goal 1, Objective 1.2) and promoting gender balance. However, people composing certain bodies are not bound to the ERIC by legal or hierarchical obligations, and the bodies' final composition is subject to the existing and available expertise (f. Dependency).

OBJECTIVE 2.1 REACH GENDER EQUALITY IN DECISION-MAKING, EXECUTIVE AND CONSULTING BODIES					
Measure 2.1.1 Promote gender balance in the EPOS bodies					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS ERIC Committees, Boards, Working Groups, Decision-Making and consulting bodies	Number of genders in committees, boards, and working groups. Means of verification: internal analysis of gender components	Available expertise	Executive Director Management and Operation Unit	2023-2024	Ongoing activity

OBJECTIVE 2.2 PROMOTE GENDER EQUALITY AT DECISION-MAKING, EXECUTIVE AND CONSULTING LEVEL					
Measure 2.2.1 Inform the existing bodies that the EPOS ERIC GEP is in place and provide them with the GEP (link)					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS ERIC Committees, Boards, Working Groups, Decision-Making and consulting bodies	Information sent to all members. Means of verification: communication distributed to stakeholders (see 1.2)	Personnel in certain bodies are not legally and hierarchically bound to EPOS ERIC	Communication Unit	2023-2024	The original version of the GEP is available on the website. A formal communication is planned for the release of the new version of the GEP (Dec23/Jan24)
Measure 2.2.2 Training the existing bodies about GEP and DEI aspects					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS ERIC Committees, Boards, Working Groups, Decision-	Training to existing bodies delivered. Means of verification: quantitative: participants list, qualitative: feedback collected from trained people	Personnel in certain bodies are not legally and hierarchically	Communication Unit	2023-2024	Measure included during 2023 GEP revision

Making and consulting bodies		bound to EPOS ERIC			
Measure 2.2.3 Include in the Rules of Procedures of boards, committees, and working groups a clause on respecting GEP and take the GEP into consideration in all the actions and decisions					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS ERIC Committees, Boards, Working Groups, Decision-Making and consulting bodies	Guidelines and training for equality-oriented language and communication (also referring to available EU material). Means of verification: new version of Rules of Procedure	Personnel in certain bodies are not legally and hierarchically bound to EPOS ERIC	Executive Director Management and Operation Unit	2023-2024	Ongoing activity. The Rules of Procedure, Section 1 are currently being updated, and the Section 2 are being developed

Goal 3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

Main objective: Ensure equality in the EPOS ERIC recruitment, selection, employment procedures, and career progression.

OBJECTIVE 3.1 GUARANTEE GENDER EQUALITY AND OTHER DEI DIMENSION IN RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION PROCEDURES					
Measure 3.1.1 Draft and disseminate calls for vacancy positions including a statement supporting equal opportunities, gender equality, diversity, and inclusiveness					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Executive Director, Recruitment Committees	The calls for vacancy include and respect gender equality policy. Means of verification: each call is reviewed against a checklist of GEP/DEI requirements	N/A	Executive Director Administration Unit	2023-2024	During 2023 no call for vacancy positions have been launched. A check-list is in place (Annex 2)
Measure 3.1.2 Usage of non-binary pronouns in vacancy advertisements					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Potential Applicants	The calls for vacancy use non-binary pronouns and gender-neutral language. Means of verification: each call is reviewed against a checklist of GEP/DEI requirements	N/A	Communication Unit	2023-2024	These practices were put in place starting with the job notices in 2023 and will be implemented from now on
Measure 3.1.3 Vacancy positions disseminated on different platforms and websites					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Potential Applicants	Number of platforms and websites used. Means of verification: statistics on vacancy posting	N/A	Communication Unit	2023-2024	These practices were put in place starting with the job notices in 2023 and will be implemented from now on
Measure 3.1.4 Gender balance in Recruitment Committee					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Executive Director, Recruitment Committee	Gender balance in the Recruitment Committee. Means of verification: each committee composition is checked against the gender balance	N/A	Executive Director Administration Unit	2023-2024	During 2023 no call for vacancy positions have been launched

OBJECTIVE 3.2 GUARANTEE GENDER EQUALITY AND OTHER DEI ASPECTS IN EMPLOYMENT PROCEDURES					
Measure 3.2.1 Employment agreement and contracts for EPOS ERIC staff includes a statement supporting equal opportunities, gender equality, diversity, and inclusiveness					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Employees	Number of agreements and contracts containing the statement. Means of verification: each agreement and contract are reviewed against the statement	N/A	Executive Director Administration Unit	2023-2024	Employment agreement and contracts respect the GEP provision

OBJECTIVE 3.3 ENSURING EQUALITY IN REMUNERATION AND CAREER PROGRESSION					
Measure 3.3.1 Provide equal salary condition					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Employees	Equal salary conditions for the same contractual level and competencies among gender. Means of verification: quantitative - gathering statistics related to agreements and contracts to assess compliance with the equal salary policy	N/A	Executive Director Administration Unit	2023-2024	Equal salary condition is provided
Measure 3.3.2 Provide equal opportunity, including training, for personnel development					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Employees	Equal assignment of responsibility and training course per employee. Means of verification: number of trainings per employee is in line with the averag	N/A	Executive Director Administration Unit Communication Unit	2023-2024	Equal training opportunity are offered in the staff training plan for 2024

Goal 4. Integrating the gender dimension into research content

Main objective: Integrate gender equality, diversity and inclusion into cultural principles, policies and across projects. In this framework linked to external activities, EPOS ERIC will strongly emphasise its commitment to the provisions of the GEP.

OBJECTIVE 4.1 INTEGRATE THE GENDER DIMENSION INTO EU-FUNDED PROJECTS IN WHICH EPOS ERIC PARTICIPATE					
Measure 4.1.1 Research team respects gender balance					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS Project team	Gender balance in the research team. Means of verification: gender distribution in teams tends to balance	Available expertise and availability	Management and Operation Unit	2023-2024	Gender balance has taken into account in teams' composition if expertise available (e.g., EPOS SP Advisory Board composition)

OBJECTIVE 4.2 PROMOTION OF GENDER EQUALITY AND OTHER DEI ASPECTS IN WORKSHOPS AND EVENTS					
Measure 4.2.1 Programme Committees briefed on the gender and other DEI aspects					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Programme Committees members	Gender balance and diversity in workshops and events. Means of verification: briefing to PC members done	N/A	Communication Unit	2023-2024	Measure included during 2023 GEP revision
Measure 4.2.2 Gender balance and diversity aspects considered in selecting invited speakers					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS Stakeholders	Gender balance and diversity in workshops and events. Event programme committees' members take into account the gender dimension and diversity when suggesting potential speakers to be invited. Means of verification: gender distribution in workshops/events tends to balance. Other DEI aspects are represented among speakers/panellists when possible.	Available expertise and availability	Communication Unit	2023-2024	In all workshops/events organised in the course of 2023 attention has been posed to achieving gender balance between speakers
Measure 4.2.3 Event/training attendance of people from developing countries, YRC etc. is promoted (e.g., through travel grants)					

Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
EPOS Stakeholders	Diversity in workshops and events. Means of verification: statistics of participation	Available expertise and availability	Communication Unit	2023-2024	Measure included during 2023 GEP revision

Goal 5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

Objective: Integrate effective measures for securing zero tolerance for gender-based violence in EPOS ERIC; Establish a culture of zero tolerance towards sexual harassment, violence, and discrimination.

OBJECTIVE 5.1 ESTABLISH A CULTURE OF ZERO TOLERANCE TOWARDS SEXUAL HARASSMENT, VIOLENCE AND DISCRIMINATION					
Measure 5.1.1 Drafting a Code of Conduct to prevent discrimination, sexual harassment, violence, and mobbing, which includes behaviour, reporting, investigation, support for victims and disciplinary measures and prosecution (ref. DEI)					
Target	Indicator	Dependency	Responsibility	Timeline	Status December 2023
Employees and all staff	Approval of the Code of Conduct Means of verification: code of conduct in place and communicated to main stakeholders	N/A	Executive Director Administration Unit Communication Unit	2023-2024	The code of conduct including the reporting process is under elaboration

1. Monitoring and Evaluation

With the EPOS ERIC Gender Equality Plan, EPOS ERIC is creating the structure and process to monitor progress towards gender equality in connection with all the above-mentioned goals focusing particularly on the changes required to promote future developments involving equality, diversity, inclusiveness and non-discrimination principles.

To identify emerging challenges pertaining to gender equality, an annual review of the status of the proposed measures will be conducted. If required, surveys may be initiated. The statistics of personnel of different genders, the number and gender of people applying for different positions, as well as the composition of boards, committees and working groups in terms of gender balance and inclusiveness will be collected, as applicable. Furthermore, where feasible, all the events organised by EPOS ERIC will aim to achieve gender equality and inclusiveness. The statistics will be collected and managed by the Management and Operational Unit with the support of the Communication Unit at EPOS ERIC.

The current document represents a baseline for further developments. Additional objectives and measures for gender equality and/or other types of inclusiveness will be proposed annually based on available data.

2. EPOS ERIC Commitment to diversity, inclusiveness and gender equality

Within the scope of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP), it is crucial to recognize the broader principles of Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI), which EPOS ERIC considers essential. EPOS ERIC is fully committed to creating a workplace that promotes diversity, and inclusivity, and supports the principles of equality. The organization actively seeks to attract and retain individuals from various cultural and societal backgrounds. EPOS ERIC believes in treating its colleagues and external partners with respect, regardless of factors such as gender, nationality, cultural background, abilities, religion, or sexual orientation. Any discrimination against employees and external parties based on one of those factors, or any comparable circumstance, will not be tolerated.

EPOS ERIC is committed to ensuring a safe, healthy, and accessible workplace, thus guaranteeing that everyone has an equal opportunity to participate in the community. The accessibility of its facilities and the opportunity to participate in decision-making are safeguarded by EPOS ERIC.

EPOS ERIC is fully committed to the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan in all aspects of the organisation to promote gender equality and diversity, enhance work-life balances and foster a respectful, open, and welcoming workplace culture. Furthermore, EPOS ERIC is committed to promoting gender equality and diversity in its activities to the EPOS Stakeholders.

Acknowledgement

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We wish to thank Barbara Angioni for her support in graphic design.

References

[European Strategy for Gender Equality 2020-2025](#)
[Conclusions on the New European Research Area \(ERA\)](#)
[Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans](#)

Annex 1 – ECO Survey

An internal survey was conducted in September 2022, aimed at measuring experiences and perceptions of gender equality in EPOS ERIC. The survey addressed the five goal areas identified within the GEP. The survey was sent to the EPOS ERIC Executive Coordination Office (ECO) staff. The ECO is organized into different units (or areas of activities) with specific commitments and personnel, some of whom are INGV personnel working as in-kind resources in EPOS ERIC. The ECO currently counts sixteen people including nine INGV employees. The ECO became operational in February 2019. The anonymously collected data highlight the need to have the Gender Equality Plan in place, identifying goals and direct measures to promote and support gender equality. Furthermore, some comments and suggestions have been freely provided by the EPOS ERIC Executive Coordination Office (ECO) staff. Considering the survey results, responses, and suggestions, as reported in the graphics below, the EPOS ERIC GEP is adapted to the current circumstances of EPOS ERIC and will be monitored and updated on an annual basis or when needed.

1. What is your gender identity?

11 responses

Gender Equality

2. In your opinion, is EPOS ERIC committed to gender equality?

11 responses

3. Are you aware of any actions, documents or policies supporting gender equality at EPOS ERIC?

11 responses

General comments:

EPOS ERIC actions, documents, or policies to support gender equality that have been identified by the respondents are as follows: EPOS ERIC Statutes, Implementing Rules, RRI policy Gender Equality Plan under discussion and preparation, EPOS ERIC privacy policy, EPOS ERIC call for vacancies, bargaining contracts and internal policies.

Promotion of gender equality

4. In your opinion, should EPOS ERIC further promote gender equality in its organizational culture? (i.e., employment contract, call for vacancies, policies)

11 responses

General comments:

The respondents suggested the improvement of gender equality in recruitment and career progression, avoiding stereotypes and strongly supporting the drafting and implementing of a Gender equality plan with effective actions in this regard.

Work-life balance and organizational culture

5. Are you satisfied with the current work-life balance arrangements EPOS ERIC offers?

11 responses

6. In your opinion, does EPOS ERIC offer enough flexibility in the way your work can be arranged?
11 responses

7. Have you ever experienced that EPOS ERIC discriminates on work-life balance based on gender?
11 responses

Gender balance in leadership and decision-making

8. Do you perceive that there is gender balance in EPOS ERIC senior leadership?
11 responses

9. Do you perceive that there is gender balance in the EPOS ERIC decision-making process?

11 responses

Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

10. In your opinion, are there gender-equal opportunities for career advancement inside EPOS ERIC?

11 responses

11. In your opinion, does EPOS ERIC provide sufficient training/mentoring opportunities to support career progression (e.g. courses, workshops, etc)?

11 responses

General comments:

Training and other career advancement opportunities should be promoted and offered to all members of the staff, according to their role in EPOS ERIC. More training for the ECO would strengthen the competencies and expertise of the staff and the matter should be addressed now as a part of the training plan which will be drafted to be implemented in 2023.

Integration of gender dimension into research content

12. In your opinion, does EPOS ERIC integrate the gender dimension into EU-funded projects in which it participates (e.g. foster and ensure gend... projects teams and decision-making processes)?

11 responses

Measures against gender-based violence

14. Do you think that EPOS ERIC should have a Code of Conduct in place, codifying the expected behavior of employees and in-kind contributors?

11 responses

15. Do you think that EPOS ERIC should have an Employee Harassment Complaint Procedure in place?

11 responses

16. Would you feel comfortable reporting any gender-based violence including sexual harassment at EPOS ERIC?

11 responses

General comments:

There is no reporting procedure to follow and there are no clear indications of how the process will be conducted or judged. This makes it more difficult for a complainant to be sure that actions will be taken and that there will be no consequences to their career. The suggestion is to implement confidential counsellor services.

17. In your opinion, is EPOS ERIC creating a suitable environment to prevent gender-based violence?

11 responses

Would you like to share anything else relevant to the subject of gender equality?**General comments:**

A common understanding of "gender" is according to the European organizations and projects working in this area would be beneficial for the staff of EPOS.

Annex 2 – Diversity, Equity and Inclusive (DEI) language checklist for Job notices and internship opportunities in EPOS

Creating inclusive and gender-neutral job notices and internship opportunities is essential to attract a diverse pool of candidates, and therefore instrumental in creating a diverse and equitable workplace.

The following checklist is intended to help recruiters and communications professionals in EPOS to draft such texts:

1) Avoid Gendered Language:

- Replace gendered terms (e.g., "chairman") with gender-neutral alternatives (e.g., "chairperson,").

2) Use Gender-Neutral Titles:

- Address candidates with gender-neutral titles such as "applicant," "candidate," or "individual."

3) Use Inclusive Pronouns:

- Use gender-neutral pronouns such as "they/them" when referring to candidates.

4) Avoid Age Discrimination:

- Unless there are specific limitations connected to a particular programme (e.g. scholarships), avoid specifying age requirements or using phrases that could discourage older or younger applicants.

5) Use a Culturally-Sensitive Language:

- Use inclusive language that respects different cultures and backgrounds. Avoid idiomatic expressions or slang that might be unfamiliar or offensive.

6) UDisability-Inclusive Language:

- Use language that emphasises your commitment to providing accommodations and welcomes applicants with disabilities. Avoid ableist language.

7) Avoid Stereotypes:

- Eliminate stereotypes and assumptions about gender roles, abilities, and cultural backgrounds.

8) Use an Open and Welcoming Tone of voice:

- Ensure that the job notice communicates an inclusive and welcoming atmosphere.

9) Avoid Domain-Specific Jargon:

- Whenever possible, eliminate domain-specific jargon or acronyms that may be unfamiliar to some candidates.

10) Education and Experience:

- Whenever possible, focus on the qualifications and skills needed for the role, rather than number of years of experience. Avoid restricting participation to candidates with a specific educational background.

11) Highlight DEI Commitment:

- Mention your organisation's commitment to diversity, equity, and inclusion in the job notice. Include an equal opportunity statement that encourages individuals from all backgrounds to apply.

12) Include Salary Ranges:

- Provide salary ranges to promote transparency and reduce wage gaps.

13) Contact Information for Inquiries:

- Provide contact information for candidates to ask questions or seek clarifications regarding the job opportunity.

14) Accessible Format:

- Make sure that the job notice complies with all accessibility provisions and guidelines, and can be optimally accessible to individuals with disabilities, such as using screen reader-friendly formats and fonts.

15) Sensitivity Review:

Have a diverse group of team members review the job notice for potential biases and insensitivity.

16) Check for Unconscious Bias:

- Be aware of unconscious bias when selecting descriptors for the role and its requirements. You can take implicit association tests to enhance your awareness about potential unconscious bias regarding a certain group
<https://implicit.harvard.edu/implicit/takeatest.html>

17) Test Language:

- Run the job notice through gender-neutral and inclusive language tools to identify potential issues. Some free tools to test your language against unconscious biases include:
 - gender-decoder.katmatfield.com
 - <https://www.totaljobs.com/insidejob/gender-bias-decoder/>
 - <https://textanalysis.beapplied.com/>

18) Feedback Loop:

- Encourage candidates to provide feedback on the job notice and recruitment process to continually improve inclusivity.

Remember that inclusive language is an ongoing practice, and it's important to stay updated on best practices and be open to evolving your approach to reflect a diverse and equitable workplace.

DEI Statements

1) Statement for job and internship notices

In EPOS, we believe that diversity is an invaluable asset to our organisation. Fostering a diverse, equitable and inclusive workplace stands therefore as a priority for us. We wholeheartedly encourage applications from individuals representing diverse ethnicities, cultural and religious backgrounds, genders, sexual orientations, and individuals at all career stages for all our job and internship opportunities.

2) Statement for training courses, summer schools etc.

EPOS is firmly dedicated to advancing diversity, equality and inclusion in every training opportunity we offer. We invite registrations from individuals of diverse ethnicities, cultural and religious backgrounds, genders, sexual orientations, and at all stages of their careers.

